

Original Article

Knowledge and Practices of Parents of Children with Asthma- A Hospital-based Study

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Abstract

Background: Asthma is becoming increasingly prevalent among children. Poor parent knowledge leads to inappropriate management practices.

Objective: To evaluate the knowledge and practices of parents of children with asthma.

Methodology: A cross sectional study was conducted in asthma center of Institute of Child and Mother Health, Matuail, Dhaka during December, 2014 to July, 2017. The diagnosis of asthma was made on the basis of case definition of asthma according to National Guideline of Bangladesh. A 30-item questionnaire was devised for this purpose. Range of score in knowledge section was 0-4 and in practice section, 0-15. The higher the score, the better the knowledge and practice of parents.

Results: Total 210 parents of children with asthma were interviewed, 57.6% (121/210) of them were male. In this study knowledge of parents regarding asthma was found poor in 20%, some in 67.1% and good in 12.9% of respondents respectively. Average score of the parents in practice section was higher in parents of doctor diagnosed asthma children than in parents of children without a prior diagnosis (6.57 ± 1.38 versus 5.36 ± 1.64).

Conclusion: Overall, knowledge and practice of parents regarding asthma was found poor.

Key words: Asthma, knowledge, practice, parents.

Introduction:

Asthma is a common chronic disease and remains an important public health issue, especially among the pediatric population.¹⁻⁴ Childhood asthma represents a significant burden, not only in terms

of morbidity and reduced quality of life but also in terms of healthcare costs, as reflected by the high rates of unscheduled emergency department visits, hospitalization, and school absenteeism.⁵ In developing countries, the terms chest allergy and dyspnea are commonly used instead of asthma to avoid the social stigma associated with the chronic nature of the disease.⁶ Prevalence of bronchial asthma among secondary school students in Dhaka city was found to be 11.6%,⁷ mostly attributed to lifestyle changes owing to the modernization of Bangladesh society, the accompanying changes in dietary habits, and increasing exposure to environmental factors such as indoor allergens, dust, sand storms, and tobacco.⁸ Parents are deemed to be the best judges of the severity of asthma because they can identify the symptoms as well as recognize their child's particular asthma pattern by careful, frequent observation.⁹ Moreover, they are also familiar with

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the triggering factors, such as tobacco smoke and diet. Parental education is important for adherence to a treatment regimen. It is important to highlight the role of medications in asthma control and management because asthmatic children and their parents must understand and cooperate with new approaches to asthma care and control.¹⁰ Parental perceptions and practices are crucial for improving the asthma outcomes in children; indeed, evidence shows that parents of asthmatic children harbor considerable misperceptions of the disease, and they often do not relate medication use to the prevention of asthma attacks.⁶ Thus, the aim of this study was to investigate the knowledge and practices of parents toward asthma and its management in Bangladeshi children.

Methodology:

A cross sectional study was conducted in asthma center of Institute of Child and Mother Health, Matuail, Dhaka during December, 2014 to July, 2017. The diagnosis of asthma was made on the basis of case definition of asthma according to National Guideline of Bangladesh. Knowledge and practices were assessed by a structured 30 item questionnaire designed for this study with the help of asthma experts and finalized after pilot testing. The 30-item questionnaire comprised four parts: (1) information regarding socio-economic condition of the parents of children with asthma; (2) asthma status of children (3) parent knowledge and (5) parent practices. Total 210 parents of children with asthma were interviewed after taking written informed consent. Knowledge was assessed by four multiple response questions; each correct response was awarded one point and incorrect response was given zero. Total marks that can be obtained by a respondent in knowledge section ranges from 0 to 4. According to marks or score obtained, the respondent was categorized as having good knowledge (4), some knowledge (2-3) and poor or no knowledge (0-1). Two types of practices were assessed for the study. One was parent practice during asthma attack of children and the other was parent practice regarding caring of children and adherence to treatment given by doctor. Each correct response was awarded two points and incorrect response was given either one or zero; score obtained in practice section ranges from 0 to 15. The higher the score, the better was the practice.

Results:

Total 210 parents of children with asthma were interviewed, 57.6% (121/210) of them were male. Their average age was 7.23 ± 3.56 years. More than half (61.4%) of the father of children had higher education (higher secondary or higher) and a little more than two third (69.0%) of the families monthly income was less than 10000 taka. Less than half (36.7%) of the fathers was current daily smoker.

A little more than two-third (68.6%) children had history of previous respiratory distress or asthma like attack and of them, 75.7% (109/144) was labeled as asthma by their doctors. Most of the children (84.8%) experienced wheezing at least once in life; 97.2% (173/178) of which had the experience within last one year. A little more than half of children (61.9%) had their onset of asthma within the first two years of their life. For most of the children, asthma was triggered by cold attack (75.2%), followed by play activity (16.7%). There was no specific season of the attack- for most of the children (70.5%), it occurred round the year. Night time attack was also found to occur most (82.4%). A little more than half (55.7%) of the children had atopy: allergic rhinitis (49.5%) and eczema (6.2%) respectively. Family members of a little more than half (57.6%) of the children were found atopic: of them, 49.6% (60/121) had asthma, 38.8% (47/121) had allergic rhinitis (22.4%) and 11.6% (14/121) had eczema respectively.

In this study, knowledge of parents regarding asthma was found poor in 20%, some in 67.1% and good in 12.9% of respondents respectively. About one fifth of the parents (19.5%) had agreed that asthma is an allergic disease. Only 11.4% parents thought it as a genetic disease. About half of the parents (50.5%) told that asthma is caused by cold. Most of the parents (81.4%) thought that asthma is not curable but can be controlled with regular treatment (Table-I).

Average score of the parents in practice section was higher in parents of doctor diagnosed asthma children than in parents of children without a prior diagnosis (6.57 ± 1.38 versus 5.36 ± 1.64). Only about one fourth of the parents (23.3%) score was above 8. About one fifth of the parents (19.5%) had given salbutamol in nebulized form to their children at home and a little more than half of the parents (54.8%) took the children to qualified doctor or hospital (Table-II).

Among the doctor diagnosed asthma patients (number-109), only about one third of the children- (32.1%) were taken regularly (one in every 6 months) to doctor. Inhaled corticosteroid was advised for 32 children, of which only 34.4% children were found to take that regularly. Oral

leukotriene antagonist was advised for 73 children; of which a little more than half (56.2%) of the children were found to take that regularly. Only negligible number of parents used face mask to their children when taken outside (7.3% among doctor diagnosed asthma children versus 5.4% among others).

Table I
Knowledge of parents towards asthmatic children

Answer of knowledge related questions	Positive answer
Asthma is an allergic disease	41(19.5)
Asthma is a genetic disease	24(11.4)
Asthma is an inflammatory disease	1(0.5)
Not sure about type of disease	136(64.8)
Asthma is caused by cold	106(50.5)
Asthma is caused by allergen	25(11.9)
Caused by a combination of both cold and allergen	29(13.8)
Not sure about the cause of disease	50(23.8)
Asthma is a curable disease	34(16.2)
Asthma is not curable, but can be controlled with regular treatment	171(81.4)
Asthma is not curable	2(1.0)
Can be cured with inhaler treatment	27(12.9)
Can be controlled with inhaler treatment	1(0.5)
Not sure about inhaler treatment	180(85.7)

*Values expressed as numbers (n) and percentages (%) in parentheses, as appropriate.

Table II
Practice of parents during asthma attack

Practicesn	Frequency
Taken to hospital or qualified doctor	115 (54.8)
Taken to homeopathic or kobirazi or nonqualified practitioner	61 (29.0)
Given salbutamol in nebulized form at home	41 (19.5)
Given oral salbutamol and or prednisolone and or antibiotic	54 (25.7)

*Values expressed as numbers (n) and percentages (%) in parentheses, as appropriate.

Table III
Practice of parents regarding caring of children and adherence to treatment given by doctor (among doctor diagnosed asthma children, n= 109)

Practices	Frequency
Regular visit to physician (one in every six month)	35 (32.1)
Regular use of inhaled corticosteroid- every day for at least three months (n=32)	11 (34.4)
Regular use of leukotriene antagonist- every day for at least six months) (n=73)	41 (56.2)
Avoidance of smoking at home	42 (38.5)
Protection of children from being exposed to dust	8 (7.3)

*Values expressed as numbers (n) and percentages (%) in parentheses, as appropriate.

Discussion

The Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA)¹¹ and the asthma guidelines for prevention and treatment written by an expert panel from the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute¹² emphasize the importance of promoting a standardized classification of asthma treatment.

In this analysis of the KP of Bangladeshi parents of children with asthma, a gap was observed between recommended and actual practices, and their overall asthma-related knowledge was also not good.

Rea et al.¹³ found that a lack of asthma-related knowledge and non-compliance to treatment are risk factors for asthma fatality. A survey in India, more than half of parents (54%) were not aware of the nature of asthma.¹⁴ In this study, a little more than this number of parents (64.8%) was also not sure about the nature of disease asthma is, which was consistent to the above study.

In a study on parental perceptions of asthma of Saudi population revealed that 53.5% of parents of asthmatic children believed that asthma is solely a hereditary disease and interestingly 77% reported the dust or allergen a potent trigger factor.¹⁵ In this study, only 11.4% parents thought that asthma was hereditary and 19.5% parents thought allergen as triggering factor.

The study in Saudi Arabia¹⁵ showed parental practices towards asthmatic children; where about 82.7% parents use 5 β -agonist, while only 7.2% use inhaled steroids; which does not meet the guidelines of Saudi Initiative for Asthma (SINA) with regard to the usage of inhaled corticosteroids. In this study, about one fifth of the parents used salbutamol in nebulized form at home (19.5%), one fourth of the parents (25.7%) used oral salbutamol and or prednisolone and or antibiotic and among parents advised for regular use of inhaled steroid by doctor, only about one third (34.4%) was found compliant.

Conclusions:

Knowledge and practice of parents of children with asthma was found poor in this study. Prior diagnosis and counseling by doctor improved practice score a little, but it indicates that improved knowledge can possibly improve practice of parents regarding childhood asthma.

References:

1. T. Hazir, C. Das, F. Piracha, B. Waheed, and M. Azam, "Carers' perception of childhood asthma and its management in a selected Pakistani community," *Archives of Disease in Childhood*, vol. 87, no. 4, pp. 287–290, 2002.
2. K. A. Riekert, A. M. Butz, P. A. Eggleston, K. Huss, M. Winkelstein, and C. S. Rand, "Caregiver-physician medication concordance and undertreatment of asthma among inner-city children," *Pediatrics*, vol. 111, no. 3, pp. 214–220, 2003.
3. R. J. Adams, A. Fuhlbrigge, J. A. Finkelstein et al., "Use of inhaled anti-inflammatory medication in children with asthma in managed care settings," *Archives of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine*, vol. 155, no. 4, pp. 501–507, 2001.
4. P. Callery, L. Milnes, C. Verduyn, and J. Couriel, "Qualitative study of young people's and parents' beliefs about childhood asthma," *British Journal of General Practice*, vol. 53, no. 488, pp. 185–190, 2003.
5. E. Pniewska and R. Pawliczak. The involvement of phospholipases A2 in asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Mediators of Inflammation*, vol. 2013, Article ID 793505, 12 pages, 2013.
6. R. Zaraket, M. A. Al-Tannir, A. A. Bin Abdulhak, A. Shatila, and H. Lababidi. Parental perceptions and beliefs about childhood asthma: a cross-sectional study. *Croatian Medical Journal*, vol. 52, no. 5, pp. 637–643, 2011.
7. Kabir ML, Rahman F, Hasan MQ et al. Asthma, atopic exzema and allergic rhinoconjunctivitis in school children. *Mymensingh medical journal: MMJ* 2005; 14(1):41.
8. B. R. Al-Ghamdi, A. A. Mahfouz, I. Abdelmoneim, M. Y. Khan, and A. A. Daffallah. "Altitude and bronchial asthma in southwestern Saudi Arabia," *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 17–23, 2008.
9. M. S. Ostergaard, "Childhood asthma: parents' perspective—a qualitative interview study," *Family Practice*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 153–157, 1998.

10. “National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute, National Institutes of Health; World Health Organization. Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA),” NHLBI, Bethesda, Md, USA; WHO, Geneva, Switzerland, 2009, <http://ginasthma.org/>.
11. The Global Initiative for Asthma. Pocket guide for asthma management and prevention, Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA) 2011 [EB/OL]. (2011-12) [2012- 07-01]. <http://www.ginasthma.org/guidelines-pocket-guide-for-asthmamanagement.html>
12. National Asthma Education and Prevention Program: Expert Panel Report 3 (EPR-3): Guidelines for the Diagnosis and Management of Asthma-Summary Report 2007. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2007, 120:S94–S138.
13. Rea H, Sears M, Beaglehole R, Fenwick J: Lessons from the national asthma mortality study: deaths in hospital. *NZ med J* 1987, 100(821):199–202.
14. Shivbalan S, Balasubramanian S, Anandnathan K: What do parents of asthmatic children know about asthma? An Indian perspective. *Indian J Chest Dis Allied Sci* 2005, 47(2):81–87.
15. Amani K, Abu-Shaheen, Abdullah Nofal, Humariya Heena. Parental Perceptions and Practices toward Childhood Asthma. *BioMed Research International: Volume 2016, Article ID 6364194, 7 pages* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2016/6364194>.
16. Al-Moamary MS, Alhaider SA, Alangari AA et al. The Saudi Initiative for Asthma - 2019 Update: Guidelines for the diagnosis and management of asthma in adults and children. *Ann Thorac Med* 2019;14:3-48.